

PECULIARITIES OF THE REPRESSIVE POLICY CARRIED OUT BY THE SOVIETS IN KHOREZM

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the cultural and educational environment of Khorezm during the period of socialist ideology. The contradiction between the methodology of culture and its development are presented.

It is necessary to reflect the truth, the bitter truth, even in the deep and comprehensive study of the pitiful, sad and tragic pages of our history. One of the dreamy pages of our history is the repressive policy of the Soviets in Khorezm and its tragic consequences. The years of worshiping the personality of Stalin brought heavy burdens on the people of Khorezm. In 1937-1939 alone, more than 41,000 people were arrested by the "troikas" of the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs of the Uzbek SSR. More than 37,000 of them were tried, 6,920 were shot.

The socio-political development of Uzbekistan took place in the USSR when the administrative command system with all its negative aspects was settled and strengthened, in short, it had a negative impact on the entire social and political life of the republic. There was such a serious factor that it was the absolute domination of the communist party with a class ideology in the political system of the Soviet sovereign state. The second half of the 1920s and 1930s was a period of extensive repression against those who opposed the regime. The non-party groups that brought together the patriotic leaders of the republic, named "Group of 18", "Inoghomovchilik", "Kasimovchilik", were exposed and discredited. The Soviet regime struck down many representatives of the national creative intelligentsia who spoke out against their leaders.

From August 10, 1937 to January 1, 1938, a total of 10,700 people were imprisoned in Uzbekistan, of which 3,613 people were sentenced to death under the 1st category, and 7,087 people were sentenced to 8-10 years of imprisonment under the 2nd category. Culture workers working in Uzbekistan at that time were not left out of these evils. One of them was Kurban Beregin from Khorezm, the chairman of the board of the State Publishing House of Uzbekistan. Kurban Beregin was born in December 1904 in the city of Khiva in the family of the miller Ollabergan. He studied at the old school from the age of 8-9, i.e. from 1912-1913. From 1917, he started studying at the madrasa. The victim has been working as a laborer since he was 12 years old. 16-year-old Kurban is brought up in an orphanage in Khiva and continues his studies.

In 1920, the Khorezm Youth Union was founded. The victim also becomes a member of this union. The dream of devoting his whole life to the people and the Motherland began to ignite in his heart from that time. Q. Beregin was sent to study at the Communist University of the Peoples of the East in Moscow with the referral of the Central Committee of the Khorezm Komsomol. However, due to the fact that the climatic conditions here are not suitable for his health, Kurban returns to Khiva on the advice of doctors, and soon he is elected as the secretary of the city's Komsomol cell. Later, in the summer of 1924, Kurban Beregin was appointed as an instructor to the Central Committee of the Khorezm Komsomol. Q. Beregin took the work very seriously and did it seriously. He participated in plenums of district and city Komsomol committees, various conferences, gave lectures and speeches on various topics. Among them, "Educational work and fight against illiteracy", "Fight against marriage of young girls", "Life of young artisans" and others are very important. Taking into account his great passion for journalism, Khiva elected Beregin as an honorary correspondent in 1924 to cover the activities of the Khiva Komsomol organization. His poems "To Working Peasants", "Eastern Women", "Eastern Girl" and the article "Our Task" were published in 1924, and the important events of that time were expressed. No matter what front he was working on, he began to faithfully fulfill the instructions of the central committee and the instructions of the party. He went to the front line in the fight against religion and took the meaningless surname "Beregin" by "sawing" the word Allah from his surname. He considered the Soviet state to be his homeland. Kurban Beregin, who works honestly and earnestly for the construction of socialism, soon became known throughout the republic as a skilled organizer. In September 1933, he worked as the head of the publishing and press department of the Central Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. There is no doubt that numerous publications of scientific and artistic works created or translated by creative people of Uzbekistan will play an important role in increasing the cultural and educational level of the people, and in the formation of educated, knowledgeable intellectual potential generations. That is why Kurban Beregin, in his article in the joint issue of "Book and Revolution" magazine, which he edited during these years, in the joint issue of 9-10, 1933, wrote happily about the year-by-year growth of book publishing in the country. The figure was 11,952 soums. Kurban Beregin points out that the main reason for the development of book publishing and trade is the increase in the level of literary and scientific works, the improvement of book publishing techniques, the shortening of the publishing period, and the decrease in the price of books. Directly under his leadership, 1212 books in 20 titles were sent to Khorezm district in November 1934.

By the spring of 1938, 60 percent of the secretaries of the provincial, city and district party committees were imprisoned. At this point, it is necessary to dwell on the activities of Karim Boltaev and Davlat Rizaev from Khorezm, who dedicated themselves to public service. Karim Boltaev, who was born in 1901 in the city of Khiva in a poor peasant family, was elected the first secretary of the Khiva District Komsomol Committee in January 1922. Later, Karim Boltaev, who was the first secretary of Khorezm Komsomol, was appointed the head of the Main Political Department of the USSR on February 16, 1924. In addition, Karim Boltaev works in Samarkand and Fergana regions. In August 1932, Karim Boltaev was appointed People's Commissar of Land Affairs of the Uzbek SSR.

Later, Karim Boltaev worked in Andijan for a year. On August 31, 1937, Karim Boltaev was recommended as the first secretary of the Karakalpakstan Oblast Party Committee. After arriving in the city of Tortkol on September 2, he began to work with a unique organization and business. But here he could not do what he intended. Karim Boltaev, who was imprisoned as an enemy of the people, was removed from the party after listening to the information of Stein, the head of the NKVD of the KK ASSR, at the office of the regional party committee held on October 11, 1937. Karim Boltaev's life ended tragically in October 1938. At the same time that the cult of personality was condemned and democratization started in the country, the case of Karim Boltaev was re-examined, he was found innocent, and he was fully acquitted in 1956.

During the period of repression, there were even cultural workers who committed suicide, saying that the accusations against them were wrong. One of them is Davlat Rizaev. He was born in February 1903 in the city of Urganch in a working family. Davlat, who is clever by nature, first studied in the old school, and later studied in the modern school of the new method.

At the beginning of 1922, Davlat Rizaev was appointed the head of the department of organizational affairs of the Central Committee of the Khorezm Komsomol, and a little later, he was elected the responsible secretary of the Central Committee. In May 1934, Davlat Rizaev was appointed deputy chairman of the Party Control Committee of the Central Committee of the CPSU (b) for Uzbekistan. During the period of 1935-1936, during the wide-scale inspection and replacement of party documents, Davlat Rizaev saw that many conscientious and businessmen were being punished on baseless charges, but he did not always have the opportunity to help them. Later, some of the actions of Davlat Rizaev were judged inappropriately and caused him to be severely punished.

No matter how hard the state tried to prove that Rizaev did not betray the cause of the people, he could not succeed, they did not believe him. A. Ikramov said that there were no revealing documents against Davlat Rizaev and there were only some rumours. Some time later, on August 3, 1937, Davlat Rizaev was arrested. He was subjected to unbearable torture in the hospital. As a result, Davlat Rizaev, who could not bear the pain and unfair slander, committed suicide on September 30, 1937. He wrote 2 letters before his death. One of the letters reads: "I have never been a nationalist or a Trotskyite. They wrote false instructions, tortured me for two months, and finally declared me a nationalist and a Trotskyist. I preferred death to this sentence." Davlat Rizaev wrote another letter to his wife.

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